

Start on Sustainability Starter Kit

1. SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS OPERATIONS

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ABOUT OUR PROJECT

By implementing Start on Sustainability, we aim **to equip micro-enterprises** with the necessary **tools and resources** to take meaningful action towards sustainability, thereby contributing to a more sustainable and resilient EU economy.

SOS Starter Kit Table of Contents

UNIT NAME	UNIT NAME
Introduction to the SOS Starter Kit	Unit 7- Supply Chain Transparency
Unit 1- Sustainable Business Operations	Unit 8- Benchmark Practices
Unit 2- Sustainable Thinking	Unit 9- Digital Tools
Unit 3- Engaging Staff	Unit 10- Pitfalls in Sustainable Businesses
Unit 4- Serving Green Consumers	Summary to the SOS Starter Kit
Unit 5- Community Partnerships	Key Terms and Definitions
Unit 6- Assessment and Planning	References

01

**SUSTAINABLE
BUSINESS
OPERATIONS**

TABLE OF CONTENTS

- 01** Introduction to the module
- 02** Sustainable Business Operations
- 03** Case Studies
- 04** Assessment
- 05** Key terms and definitions
- 06** References

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01

OVERVIEW OF THE TOPIC

02

OBJECTIVES

03

LEARNING OUTCOMES

OVERVIEW

Topic 1: Understanding of Sustainability

Learners will cover the principles of sustainability in business, recognizing how to integrate and balance environmental, social, and economic factors in their micro business.

Topic 2: Practical Application of Sustainable Practices

Learners will acquire the skills to implement key sustainable practices such as waste reduction, energy efficiency, and sustainable sourcing within their business operations.

Topic 3: Regulatory Insight and Stakeholder Engagement

Learners will understand and navigate the regulatory landscape affecting their business, and learn how to engage stakeholders effectively to communicate sustainability efforts.

Topic 4: Performance Measurement and Business Competitiveness

Learners will be able to use various tools and metrics to measure their sustainability performance and leverage this data to enhance their business's long-term competitiveness and market position.

OBJECTIVES

- Gain a robust understanding of sustainability in the business context, including defining sustainability, recognising sustainable business models like circular economy and shared value, and balancing environmental, social, and economic factors.
- Acquire knowledge and skills to apply eco-efficient practices such as waste reduction, energy efficiency, and sustainable sourcing, alongside developing and implementing a tailored sustainability plan for business improvement.

OBJECTIVES

Understand and navigate the regulatory landscape, utilise available incentives, and effectively communicate and report sustainability efforts to stakeholders to enhance engagement and transparency.

Learn to use tools and metrics for measuring sustainability performance, evaluate business operations, and understand how integrating sustainability can enhance long-term business competitiveness and market position.

LEARNING OUTCOMES

In this module, you will learn the basics of sustainability in business. This includes information such as how to define and balance environmental, social, and economic aspects. You will also acquire skills to implement practices such as waste reduction, energy efficiency, and sustainable sourcing, and develop a sustainability plan tailored to your business.

You will also build knowledge on understanding how to navigate regulatory requirements, and use incentives to support sustainable operations. You will also learn how to communicate your sustainability efforts to stakeholders, using metrics to measure and evaluate your business's sustainability performance, helping enhance its long-term competitiveness and market position.

02

SUSTAINABLE BUSINESS OPERATIONS

01

Topic 1: Understanding Business Sustainability

02

Topic 2: Practical Application of Sustainable Practices

03

Topic 3: Regulatory Insight and Stakeholder Engagement

04

Topic 4: Performance Measurement and Business Competitiveness

02.1

Topic 1: Understanding Business Sustainability

Defining Sustainability in Business

Sustainability in business refers to the capacity of companies to operate in a manner that ensures long-term ecological balance, social equity, and economic viability. This concept emphasises the importance of not just profitability, but also the need for practices that protect the environment and contribute positively to society

Defining Sustainability in Business

The importance of sustainability in the modern business is increasingly critical. Companies are expected not only to provide economic value but also to operate responsibly in a way that minimises environmental damage and maximises benefits to society. This shift is driven by changing consumer preferences, stricter regulatory environments, and the urgent need to address global challenges like climate change, resource depletion, and social inequality.

Profit, People, Planet

Business sustainability involves managing the triple bottom line, which encompasses a company's approach to balancing its economic, social, and environmental priorities. These three dimensions are commonly known as profit, people, and planet. In practical terms, this includes:

- **Profit:** Sustaining long-term economic stability and growth of the business.
- **People:** Being accountable for the impact of business practices on employees, customers, communities, and all other stakeholders.
- **Planet:** Reducing environmental footprints and preserving natural resources across all business activities.

The Three Pillars of Sustainability

To fully understand business sustainability, it's essential to look at its three foundational pillars:

- Environmental Sustainability
- Social sustainability
- Economic Sustainability

The Three Pillars of Sustainability

1. Environmental Sustainability:

This involves your company's approach to minimising its ecological footprint. By implementing practices that reduce waste and pollution, conserving resources, and promoting the use of renewable energy, businesses can mitigate their impact on the environment.

2. Social Sustainability:

Social sustainability focuses on the impact of the company on its employees and the communities where it operates. This includes ensuring fair labour practices, community engagement, supporting social equity, and investing in employee well-being.

3. Economic Sustainability:

Economic sustainability ensures that a business operates on a financially sound basis while considering its long-term impact on the environment and society. This includes profitable operations that also contribute positively to the social and environmental goals.

Why Does Business Sustainability Matter?

The importance of sustainability in business cannot be overstated. It helps to ensure businesses can thrive and adapt in a rapidly changing world with dwindling natural resources, shifting regulatory landscapes, and evolving consumer expectations.

Sustainable businesses are better positioned to:

- Attract and retain talent.
- Drive innovation and open new markets.
- Improve operational efficiencies and reduce costs.
- Enhance brand reputation and customer loyalty.
- Reduce risks associated with overuse of resources and regulatory non-compliance.

02.2

Topic 2: Practical Application of Sustainable Practices

**“We don't inherit the earth from our ancestors,
we borrow it from our children”
Native American Proverb**

This topic focuses on applying sustainable practices within business operations to enhance environmental benefits and improve business performance.

Learners will explore actionable strategies that integrate sustainability into everyday business functions.

You will understand how to implement sustainable practices in business settings, and make informed decisions and ethical choices that benefits operational efficiency and reputation.

Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy Solutions

Energy management is a fundamental aspect of sustainable business practices. Energy audits can help businesses identify key areas where energy consumption can be optimised.

Transitioning to energy-efficient appliances and systems, such as LED lighting and high-efficiency HVAC systems, can significantly reduce energy use. Investing in renewable energy sources such as solar or wind energy not only cuts down on greenhouse gas emissions but also stabilises energy costs over time. This can help to safeguard against fluctuating energy prices.

[Find out more ways you can make your business more energy efficient by clicking on this link](#)

Waste Management and Reduction

The first step in waste management is reducing the amount of waste generated. Businesses can achieve this by re-evaluating their production processes, product designs, and everyday operational practices to identify areas where waste can be minimised.

Process optimisation involves refining production workflows to increase efficiency, reduce costs, and minimise waste. This typically includes upgrading equipment and streamlining operations to use resources more effectively.

Additionally, material substitutions replace single-use or non-recyclable items with alternatives like biodegradable packaging. Company-wide policies further support waste reduction by promoting digital documentation and reducing single-use items in offices and cafeterias.

Recycling and Reuse Programs

After establishing waste reduction measures, attention turns to managing residual waste through effective recycling and reuse programs:

Comprehensive Recycling: Implement a structured recycling program that clearly outlines which materials can be recycled and how. Training employees on proper sorting and disposal is key to ensuring compliance.

Creative Reuse: Encourage repurposing materials within business operations, such as using scrap from one process as input for another.

Partnerships for Waste Handling: Collaborate with specialised waste management companies to ensure responsible processing of materials.

Water Conservation Techniques

For micro enterprises and small businesses, implementing water conservation is both practical and vital, helping to manage resources efficiently and reduce operational costs. Developing a basic water management plan is crucial; this could start with conducting simple audits to understand water usage patterns and identifying leaky fixtures for immediate repair.

Educating employees or family members involved in the business about the importance of water conservation can increase responsible usage habits. Micro enterprises can also contribute to community efforts in water conservation, thereby enhancing environmental sustainability locally and at the same time cultivating positive business reputation.

[Click here to find out more ways a business can reduce its water consumption](#)

Sustainable Sourcing and Supply Chains

Sustainable sourcing is essential for maintaining ethical and environmentally friendly supply chains. Choosing suppliers who follow sustainable practices enhances a business's sustainability credentials and ensures compliance with global standards.

Opting for sustainable materials in products reduces environmental harm and meets the growing consumer demand for eco-friendly products. Regular supply chain audits ensure ongoing compliance and improvement, strengthening a company's sustainability profile.

Fair Trade and Labor Practices involve ensuring that all workers in the supply chain are treated ethically and receive fair wages, promoting a just and equitable workplace environment.

[Click here to find out more](#)

Corporate Culture and Sustainability

Corporate culture and sustainability are closely linked, particularly in micro and small businesses where integrating environmental and social values into the organisation can significantly impact operations and reputation.

A focus on sustainability enhances employee engagement and drives innovation. Leadership is crucial in embedding these values throughout the business. This culture attracts employees who prioritise sustainability and thus fosters a collaborative environment conducive to innovative practices.

Challenges like resistance to change and balancing sustainability with profitability are common, but the long-term benefits, such as improved customer loyalty, better brand reputation, and compliance with environmental standards, often outweigh these obstacles, making sustainability a strategic choice for small businesses.

[Click here for more information](#)

02.3

Topic 3: Regulatory Insight and Stakeholder Engagement

Understanding the EU Regulatory Landscape

For micro enterprises in the EU, understanding and complying with sustainability-related regulations is important. The EU has a comprehensive framework of environmental and social regulations that small businesses must navigate.

These can include directives on waste management, energy efficiency, and emissions, as well as regulations on labour rights and community engagement.

Key EU Regulations to Consider

Navigating regulatory requirements and engaging stakeholders are essential for implementing sustainable practices in EU micro enterprises. Here are three types regulations to know:

Environmental Regulations: EU directives such as the Waste Framework Directive and the Eco-design Directive mandate specific waste management practices and energy-efficient product design.

Key EU Regulations to Consider

Social Regulations: The EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and directives on labour rights ensure the protection of personal data and promote fair labour practices.

Economic Regulations: Financial incentives such as reduced VAT rates for green products and subsidies for renewable energy initiatives can help small businesses manage costs while implementing sustainable practices.

Using Incentives to Support Sustainable Operations

The EU offers various incentives designed to support the adoption of sustainable practices by small businesses. These include funding opportunities through programs like Horizon Europe for innovation and sustainability projects, regional development funds, and specific incentives for energy efficiency and renewable energy investments. For example, a micro enterprise might be able to use EU grants for installing renewable energy solutions such as solar panels or biomass heating systems, reducing long-term energy costs and enhancing sustainability.

Using Incentives to Support Sustainable Operations

Similarly, tax relief and investment grants might be available for small businesses that invest in eco-innovative technologies, helping offset initial investment costs and encourage sustainable growth.

Strategies for Stakeholder Engagement

A "stakeholder" refers to any individual, group, or organisation that has an interest in or is affected by the company's activities and decisions. Effective communication and engagement with stakeholders are essential for the success of sustainability initiatives within micro enterprises.

This involves regularly updating stakeholders on the business's sustainability practices and how these efforts contribute to broader environmental and social goals.

Tools for Effective Communication

Sustainability Reports: Tailored to small business contexts, reports can focus on specific sustainability achievements, challenges, and future goals.

Digital Platforms: Utilising social media and other online platforms to share updates and engage with both local and international customers and suppliers.

Communication and Engagement

Benefits of Transparent Communication:

Transparent communication can build trust and can enhance the reputation of a small or micro enterprise within the EU market. It attracts customers who are eco-conscious and can improve relations with regulators by demonstrating compliance and commitment to sustainability.

Creating Value through Engagement:

For micro enterprises, engaging stakeholders such as local communities, suppliers, and customers can lead to beneficial collaborations and innovations in sustainability. This engagement helps align business practices with community values and market expectations, which is particularly valuable in the diverse cultural landscape of the EU.

02.4

Topic 4: Performance Measurement and Business Competitiveness

Importance of Measuring Sustainability Performance

Measuring sustainability performance is essential for regulatory compliance and for improving business processes and maintaining a competitive edge, particularly for micro enterprises operating in the competitive EU market.

This typically involves assessing how well the business is adapting sustainable practices into its operations and the impact of these practices on environmental and social outcomes. Three methods we would suggest for businesses to implement are:

- Sustainability Metrics
- Lifecycle Assessment (LCA)
- Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Reporting

Sustainability Metrics

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

- To effectively monitor sustainability, micro enterprises can use Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) that track various aspects of their environmental impact. Commonly measured metrics can include:
- Carbon Footprint: Quantifies the total greenhouse gas emissions caused directly and indirectly by a business.
- Energy Usage: Monitors the amount of energy consumed, aiming to reduce usage over time through more efficient practices and technologies.
- Waste Reduction: Tracks reductions in waste generation through recycling efforts and waste management strategies.
- Water Efficiency: Measures water usage and identifies opportunities for conservation, important for areas facing water scarcity.

Lifecycle Assessment (LCA)

Lifecycle Assessment (LCA) is a critical tool used to evaluate the environmental aspects and potential impacts associated with a product, process, or service throughout its lifecycle. It helps businesses make informed decisions about product design, material selection, and end-of-life management to minimise environmental impact. This includes:

- **Raw Material Extraction:** Assessing the impact of extracting raw materials used in products.
- **Materials Processing and Manufacturing:** Evaluating the environmental costs of converting raw materials into finished products.
- **Distribution and Use:** Analysing the impact of transporting and using the product during its operational life.
- **Repair, Maintenance, and End-of-Life:** Considering the sustainability of maintaining the product and the environmental implications of product disposal or recycling.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) Reporting

ESG Reporting is an important aspect of business transparency, providing stakeholders with a comprehensive overview of a company's operations in terms of its ethical impact and sustainable practices. ESG reporting helps companies track their sustainability performance, enhancing their reputation and investor appeal. This type of reporting includes:

Environmental: This aspect evaluates how responsibly the company acts towards the environment, focusing on its efforts to minimise negative impacts and enhance ecological benefits through its operations and policies.

Social: This category assesses the company's interactions and relationships with employees, suppliers, customers, and community members. It examines the company's commitment to fair practices, community involvement, and fostering a positive impact on society.

Governance: This section analyses the company's governance structure and practices, including the integrity and effectiveness of leadership, compensation practices for executives, the thoroughness of audits, the robustness of internal controls, and the protection of shareholder rights.

Increasing Competitive Advantage

Adopting sustainable practices can distinguish micro enterprises from competitors by appealing to environmentally and socially conscious consumers. Sustainability can also lead to cost savings through more efficient resource use and potentially lower regulatory costs.

Some examples include:

Brand Differentiation: Companies that communicate their sustainability efforts effectively often enjoy enhanced brand loyalty and reputation.

Operational Efficiencies: Reduced energy consumption and waste production not only cuts costs but also potentially lower regulatory costs.

Attracting Investments: Businesses that demonstrate a strong commitment to sustainability metrics are more likely to attract investors looking for responsible investment opportunities.

Planning for the Future

For sustainability to effectively enhance business competitiveness, it must be integrated into the core business strategy. This requires a long-term outlook that aligns sustainability goals with business objectives, ensuring that sustainable practices are maintained, measured, and improved over time.

Developing a Roadmap for Implementation

Setting Realistic Goals: Based on the assessment of current sustainability metrics, set achievable yet ambitious goals that push the business towards greater sustainability.

Continuous Improvement: Implement a cycle of monitoring, reporting, and adjusting sustainability practices to respond to changes in the business environment and regulatory landscape.

[Click here to find out more](#)

03

CASE STUDIES

01

Case study 1: IKEA Case Study: Implementing Solar Energy

02

Case study 2: All About Kombucha - Sustainable Innovation in Beverage Production

03

Case study 3: BiaSol - Revolutionising Food Sustainability

Case Study 1

IKEA Case Study: Implementing Solar Energy

Introduction

IKEA, known worldwide for its flat-pack furniture and home accessories, has also been a leader in corporate sustainability efforts. Recognising the significant environmental impact and high operational costs associated with traditional energy use in their extensive global operations, IKEA embarked on an ambitious plan to transform its energy infrastructure.

The company aimed to reduce its carbon footprint and align its business practices with its sustainability ethos, which focuses on becoming climate positive and reducing more greenhouse gas emissions than the IKEA value chain emits by 2030.

Problem

As a major retailer with vast store networks and warehouses, IKEA faced substantial energy demands. These not only led to high energy bills but also conflicted with its commitment to environmental sustainability. The reliance on non-renewable energy sources was at odds with IKEA's vision to minimize its environmental impact and promote sustainable living among its customers.

Intervention

IKEA's response was a strategic investment in solar energy. The company initiated a program to install solar panels on the roofs of its stores and warehouses globally. This was part of a larger commitment to renewable energy that aimed to make IKEA stores energy-independent, significantly reducing their reliance on fossil fuels and decreasing their carbon emissions.

Outcome

The solar energy initiative proved to be highly successful. IKEA significantly cut its energy costs and reduced its carbon emissions, moving closer to its goal of becoming a net positive contributor to the environment.

This initiative not only improved IKEA's operational sustainability but also strengthened its reputation as an environmentally responsible company.

The success of this project has encouraged IKEA to continue investing in renewable energy solutions and other sustainability projects, demonstrating its commitment to positive environmental impact.

[Find out more by clicking on this link](#)

Case Study 2

All About Kombucha - Sustainable Innovation in Beverage Production

Introduction

All About Kombucha was founded in 2017 in Galway, Ireland, by Keith Loftus and Emmett Kerrigan. The founders, inspired by kombucha's health benefits discovered during a stay in Canada, aimed to introduce this health-promoting beverage to the Irish market.

However, they faced the challenge of doing so in an environmentally sustainable manner that would support local communities and align with their core values of causing minimal harm and promoting health.

To address this, All About Kombucha committed to a series of sustainable practices:

- **Sustainable Sourcing:** They prioritised using organic ingredients to ensure the purity and environmental integrity of their products.
- **Carbon-Neutral Production:** The brewery adopted carbon-neutral methods to minimise its environmental impact.
- **Zero-Waste Initiatives:** Efforts were made to minimise waste throughout their production processes.
- **Support for Local Agriculture:** The company became involved in regenerative agriculture projects and native tree planting, dedicating 10% of their brewery profits annually to these causes.
- **Community Engagement:** Beyond production, they extended their product line to include tea kits and sustainable merchandise and held workshops to educate the community on sustainable practices and nutrition.

Outcome:

All About Kombucha's comprehensive approach to sustainability has significantly enhanced their brand reputation, attracting environmentally conscious customers and contributing to community well-being.

Their commitment to environmental stewardship and local support has been instrumental in their expansion and resilience, demonstrating that business success and sustainability can go hand in hand.

The company's initiatives such as membership in 1% for the Planet and extensive community engagement have not only ensured local goodwill but have also positioned them as a leader in sustainable business practices within the beverage industry.

Case Study 3

BiaSol - Revolutionising Food Sustainability

Problem:

Founded in 2020 by siblings Ruairi and Niamh Dooley in Ireland, BiaSol was initiated to address food waste and promote sustainable nutrition by repurposing the abundant spent grain from the local craft beer industry.

This idea arose during a period of increasing global awareness around sustainable practices and healthier eating habits.

Navigating the challenges of integrating these sustainable practices into a viable business model, particularly the logistical issues related to handling and processing spent grain, was central to their mission.

BiaSol joined the Food Waste Charter of Ireland in 2023, underscoring their dedication to reducing food waste and supporting sustainable industry practices.

Intervention:

BiaSol adopted several strategic approaches to overcome these challenges:

- **Repurposing Spent Grain:** They innovated a method to dry and mill spent grain from local breweries, transforming it into a high-fiber ingredient suitable for various food products.
- **Product Development:** Leveraging Niamh's expertise in food science, the team developed a diverse range of retail products based on spent grain, thus promoting a circular economy.
- **Community Engagement and Environmental Initiatives:** The company committed to zero-waste manufacturing practices, which emphasized resource efficiency and minimal environmental impact. They also engaged in extensive community education efforts to promote sustainable living and responsible consumption.

Outcome:

- **Environmental Benefits:** By converting spent brewing grain into nutritious food products, BiaSol has significantly reduced the amount of organic waste going to landfills, thereby cutting down on greenhouse gas emissions from waste decomposition.
- **Brand Impact and Community Relations:** These sustainability efforts have not only elevated BiaSol's brand reputation as an innovator in sustainable food production but have also built a loyal consumer base that values ethical and environmentally conscious businesses.
- **Industry Leadership:** BiaSol's initiatives have established them as industry leaders, showing how sustainable practices can be effectively integrated into business models to benefit the environment, the community, and the economy

“We are the first generation to feel the effect of climate change and the last generation who can do something about it”

Barack Obama

04

ASSESSMENT

Q1

What is a primary goal of sustainable business practices?

- A) Maximising short-term profits at any cost
- B) Reducing ethical standards to increase market share
- C) Balancing environmental, social, and economic considerations
- D) Focusing exclusively on shareholder interests

Q2

Which strategy is commonly used by businesses to reduce their carbon footprint?

- A) Increasing reliance on fossil fuels
- B) Expanding office spaces and physical infrastructure
- C) Investing in renewable energy sources like solar and wind power
- D) Cutting costs through reduced waste management

Q3

Which of the following is an example of a sustainable sourcing practice?

- A) Procuring materials without regard to their origin
- B) Ignoring fair trade practices
- C) Prioritising low-cost suppliers regardless of their environmental impact
- D) Choosing suppliers who adhere to environmental and social standards

Q4

Which of the following is an example of a sustainable sourcing practice?

- A) Procuring materials without regard to their origin
- B) Ignoring fair trade practices
- C) Prioritising low-cost suppliers regardless of their environmental impact
- D) Choosing suppliers who adhere to environmental and social standards

Q5

What does LEED certification signify in a building?

- A) The building is primarily constructed from non-recycled materials
- B) It has achieved standards of energy efficiency and sustainability
- C) It uses traditional energy systems only
- D) It is free from any regulatory compliance

Answer Key

Q1: C

Q2: C

Q3: D

Q4: D

Q5: B

05

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

- **Sustainability:** The ability to maintain or improve standards of living without damaging or depleting natural resources for the future.
- **Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR):** A business model that helps a company be socially accountable to itself, its stakeholders, and the public. By practicing corporate social responsibility, companies can be conscious of the kind of impact they are having on all aspects of society, including economic, social, and environmental.
- **Triple Bottom Line:** A framework or theory that recommends that companies commit to focus on social and environmental concerns just as they do on profits. The triple bottom line consists of social equity, environmental protection, and economic profitability - three Ps: people, planet, and profit.

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

- **Carbon Footprint:** The total amount of greenhouse gases (including carbon dioxide and methane) that are generated by our actions. Lowering a carbon footprint means saving expenses as well as helping combat climate change and its effects.
- **Greenwashing:** Disinformation disseminated by an organisation so as to present an environmentally responsible public image, while its business practices may not be environmentally sustainable.
- **Circular Economy:** A regenerative approach in contrast to the traditional linear economy (make, use, dispose) to keep resources in use for as long as possible, extract the maximum value from them whilst in use, then recover and regenerate products and materials at the end of each service life.

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

- **Renewable Energy:** Energy from a source that is not depleted when used, such as wind or solar power.
- **Eco-Efficiency:** Business practices aimed at reducing ecological damage while maximizing resource efficiency.
- **Life Cycle Assessment (LCA):** The assessment of environmental impacts associated with all the stages of a product's life from raw material extraction through materials processing, manufacture, distribution, use, repair and maintenance, and disposal or recycling.
- **Sustainable Supply Chain:** Managing supply chains in ways that are environmentally sound, socially responsible, and economically viable.

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

- Ethical Sourcing: Obtaining supplies in a way that respects the environment and ensures that the workers involved in making them are safe and treated fairly
- Green Building: Building projects that would typically use sustainable materials and implement principles of sustainable architecture, which include energy efficiency, water conservation, and the use of renewable energy sources.
- Biodiversity: The variety of plant and animal life in the world or in a particular habitat, a high level of which is usually considered to be important and desirable.
- Energy Conservation: The effort made to reduce the consumption of energy by using less of an energy service.

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

- **LEED Certification:** Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design; a popular green building certification system, which provides a framework for building highly efficient and cost-saving green buildings.
- **Stakeholder Engagement:** Involvement of stakeholders in the planning, development, implementation, and continuous improvement process in a project or company.
- **Corporate Governance:** The system of rules, practices, and processes by which a firm is directed and controlled. Corporate governance essentially involves balancing the interests of a company's many stakeholders.

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

- **Recycling:** The process of converting waste materials into new materials and objects, preventing waste of potentially useful materials, reducing consumption of fresh raw materials, and reducing energy usage.
- **Regenerative Design:** A process-oriented approach to design that restores, renews, or revitalizes sources of energy and materials.
- **Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG):** Criteria are a set of standards for a company's operations that socially conscious investors use to screen potential investments. Environmental criteria consider how a company performs as a steward of nature. Social criteria examine how it manages relationships with employees, suppliers, customers, and the communities where it operates. Governance deals with a company's leadership, executive pay, audits, internal controls, and shareholder rights.

KEY TERMS AND DEFINITIONS

- **Impact Investing:** Investments made into companies, organizations, and funds with the intention to generate a measurable, beneficial social or environmental impact alongside a financial return. Impact investments provide capital to address social and/or environmental issues.
- **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs):** A collection of 17 global goals set by the United Nations General Assembly in 2015 for the year 2030. These goals are broad and interdependent, yet each has a separate list of targets to achieve. Covering social and economic development issues, these goals include poverty, hunger, health, education, climate change, gender equality, water, sanitation, energy, urbanization, environment, and social justice.

“Sustainability has to be a way of life to be a way of business”

Paul Polman

06

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Thank You

Any questions?

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